

Proteotyping microorganisms in human distal oesophagus under normal and disease conditions

Proteotyping microorganisms in oesophagus

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PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

I have read the Participant Information Sheet or someone has read it to me in a language that I understand.

I understand the purposes, procedures and risks of the research described in the project.

I give permission for my doctors, other health professionals, hospitals or laboratories outside this hospital to release information to Nepean Hospital concerning my disease and treatment for the purposes of this project. I understand that such information will remain confidential.

I have had an opportunity to ask questions and I am satisfied with the answers I have received.

I hereby freely agree to participate in this research project as described and understand that I can withdraw at any time during the study without affecting my future health care.

Name of Participant (please print) _____
Signature _____ Date _____

Name of Witness* to Participant's Signature (please print) _____
Signature _____ Date _____

* Witness is not to be the investigator, a member of the study team or their delegate. In the event that an interpreter is used, the interpreter may not act as a witness to the consent process. Witness must be 18 years or older.

Declaration by Study Doctor/Senior Researcher†

I have given a verbal explanation of the research project, its procedures and risks and I believe that the participant has understood that explanation.

Name of Study Doctor/ Senior Researcher† (please print) _____
Signature _____ Date _____

† A senior member of the research team must provide the explanation of, and information concerning, the research project.

Note: All parties signing the consent section must date their own signature.